

OPTIMUM PROCESSING PARAMETERS FOR HOT DRAPE FORMING OF OUT-OF-AUTOCLAVE PREPREG OVER COMPLEX SHAPE USING A DOUBLE DIAPHRAGM TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Hot drape formation of out-of-autoclave (OOA) prepregs is a promising manufacturing process for the aerospace and automotive industries, as it offers a reduction in overall processing time and cost. This study aims to examine the formability of out-of-autoclave 8-harness satin woven carbon/epoxy prepregs into complex shapes using a custom-made diaphragm forming set-up. In the diaphragm forming process, a composite laminate is placed between two deformable sheets, known as diaphragms. The diaphragms are then clamped, heated with the laminate to the processing temperature, and formed to the mold by applying vacuum pressure beneath the lower diaphragm. The current study carried out a double-diaphragm forming procedure at different forming rates and temperatures in order to examine the contribution of these parameters to part quality. A one-step procedure was used for both forming and curing processes using the same set-up. Observed defects, such as wrinkles, were compared against various processing parameters. In addition, the in-plane shear resistance of 8-harness satin woven carbon/epoxy prepreg prior to the forming process was investigated using a bias-extension test. The study shows that higher processing temperatures help to decrease the degree of wrinkling that occurs in the forming part. Meanwhile, the outer diameter of double-curved parts was found to conform more closely to the original shape when forming proceeded at a slower rate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite parts are manufactured using a range of techniques, both conventional and automated. However, conventional composite manufacturing techniques, such as hand lay-up, are labor intensive, time consuming, and costly. Use of automated technologies to form composite is an alternative to conventional methods that can reduce manufacturing time and cost. Hot drape forming of thermoset composites has shown promising results in the aerospace and automotive industries, where it has consistently produced a high-complexity and high-volume output [1,2]. This forming process works by transforming uncured flat laminates, created by automated technologies such as Automated Tape Laying (ATL) or Automated Fiber Placement (AFP), into three-dimensional shapes through the application of heat and pressure. This is followed by a curing process [1,3].

Double diaphragm forming is a one of the most important sheet forming process for composite materials which was initially applied to thermoplastic matrix composites. A typical double-diaphragm forming process can be described by three steps [2]. A flat laminate must first be placed between two deformable sheets known as diaphragms, which are themselves clamped over a forming box. The space between the diaphragms is subjected to a full vacuum seal. Next, the laminate between the diaphragms is heated up to processing temperature. Finally, formation takes place by applying controlled vacuum pressure to the forming-box cavity below the lower diaphragm.

Most of the previous research [4-8] focused on the diaphragm forming that use thermoplastic prepreg. They showed that forming of thermoplastic prepreg can be influenced by processing parameters [4-8], tool geometries [7,9] and diaphragm materials [5]. However, the choice of diaphragm materials is limited by the commercial availability of the desired properties. Although this process is a promising method in aerospace industry using thermosetting prepreg [10,11], there is to date a lack of research on the processing parameters that influence formability. Recently, Bian *et al.* [12] and Sun *et al.* [13] studied the effects of temperature and forming rate on the quality of C-shaped unidirectional thermosetting composite laminates during diaphragm forming. They found that low temperature and high forming rate can cause fiber wrinkling due to poor sliding of prepreg and large frictional force with the forming tool. In the diaphragm forming of thermosetting prepreg, the matrix is only heated enough to decrease the matrix viscosity so that the prepreg can be formed readily [14]. Thereafter, the curing process usually takes place in an oven or autoclave. In the present study, out-of-autoclave (OOA) prepreps were used to reduce overall processing time and cost. It is shown that the proposed double-diaphragm set-up can fully accommodate the forming and curing steps of the process, thus bypassing the need for an oven.

During the forming of double-curved parts, in-plane shear deformation is the dominant deformation mechanism [1]. This deformation mechanism for woven fabric is characterized by rotation of the yarns at their crossovers, which causes a change in fiber orientation. The rotation around weave crossover is mainly limited by the ability of fiber yarns to become in contact with each other (locking angle) [15,16]. The critical locking angle, caused by the rapid increase in force that occurs when all yarns are in contact with each other and compressed, has been found to cause wrinkling [17].

The present study aims to study the formability of the out-of-autoclave 8-harness satin woven carbon/epoxy prepreg into a double curved-shaped using double diaphragm forming process. In particular, the effect of forming rates and temperatures on the part-quality is investigated. Observed defects, such as wrinkles, are deliberated in relation to the various processing parameters. The in-plane shear angles and locking angle for the fabric, obtained through a bias extension test, are compared with the shear angles on the formed part to draw a clear conclusion about the occurrence of wrinkling.

2. EXPERIMENT

An experimental study on formability and wrinkling formation was performed for a double-curved shaped (metallic mixing bowl) with a challenging flange, as shown in Fig. 1. The tool geometry was chosen for two reasons: first, to examine the in-plane deformability, which is the dominant deformation mechanism for the selected shape, and second, to show the capabilities of the diaphragm forming process in terms of producing high-complexity parts.

Figure 1: The double-curved tool with inner diameter of 133 mm and 60 mm height.

2.1 Materials

The out-of-autoclave prepreg selected for this study was the 8-harness satin woven carbon/epoxy from Cytec Engineered Materials. The resin code is (Cycom 5320) toughened epoxy and the fabric has 3K fibers per tow. The fabric areal weight is 375 g/m² and the resin content is 36% by weight. The measured thickness of uncured one-ply is approximately 0.47 mm. From these properties, the fiber volume fraction can be calculated as

$$V_f = \frac{NM_f}{\rho_f h} \quad (1)$$

where M_f is the areal density of the fabric (kg/m²), N is the number of plies, h is the ply thickness (m), and ρ_f is the density of carbon fiber (kg/m³). Hence, fiber volume fraction is about 45%.

2.2 Double-diaphragm forming set-up

A custom-built set-up was developed at Concordia University, consisting of a vacuum system, a heating system and double-diaphragm tool, as illustrated in Fig. 2. A radiant heater from WATLOW with high performance capabilities (temperatures up to 1095 °C) and a control panel was used. The vacuum system consists of a vacuum box with a control valve and a vacuum pump, for applying vacuum pressure to the cavity between the two diaphragms and within the vacuum box. The vacuum box has a movable plate with interior holes designed to control the height of the tool. To achieve the necessary processing temperatures and to ensure a closed chamber for the curing step, the vacuum box can be adjusted using two electronic jacks. The diaphragm material used in this study was a translucent silicone rubber (EL1040T), manufactured by Torr Technologies, Inc., with 1.6 mm thickness. The double-diaphragm tool has a control valve and vacuum gage to monitor the pressure that is applied between the diaphragms. Thermocouple is used to control the processing temperature.

Figure 2: Double diaphragm forming set-up: (a) schematic and (b) photograph

2.3 Forming experiment procedure

One-ply samples were cut into 300×300 mm segments and marked with a pattern of white lines in order to measure the shear angle after the forming process. The metallic mixing bowl tool was placed in the center of the vacuum box and heated for 20 min. Thereafter, the sample is positioned in the double-diaphragm tool, as shown in Fig. 3, and preheated to the processing temperature. The forming processes were carried out at different temperatures, pressures, and forming rates (see Table 1). Vacuum pressure was applied between the two diaphragms to hold the sample during preheating and to avoid a compressive state. Both forming and curing were performed sequentially using the same forming set-up. Once the forming step is done, the vacuum box was moved up to make a closed chamber with the heater, and the temperature was raised to the curing temperature (121 °C), as recommended by the manufacturer. All the samples were kept for 60 min at the same curing temperature and conditions.

Figure 3: Marked sample inside the double-diaphragm tool

Sample	Forming temperature (°C)	Applied Pressure within box (kPa)	Forming rate (kPa/sec)
1,2,3	50,70,90	85	10
5	90	30	10
6,7	90	85	1.6,0.3

Table 1: Forming experiment conditions

2.4 In-plane shear deformability

A bias extension test was used in this study to investigate in-plane shear deformability at the forming temperatures described above. The degree of in-plane shear for woven fabric is indicated by the shear angle between the weft and warp yarns. When this shear angle becomes locked, wrinkles may occur; much previous research validates this claim [18,19]. More details about bias extension kinematics can be found in [20,21]. The specimens selected were 150 mm long by 50 mm wide, with an un-gripped length of 100 mm. The tests were performed using a tensile testing machine, as well as a non-contacted infrared heater

for the elevated-temperature tests. In order to ensure uniform heating during the elevated-temperature tests, the specimen was held at the same heat for 10 minutes after reaching the processing temperature. Two digital cameras took regular snapshots of the test to assist in the measurement of the shear angle and to capture the onset of wrinkling.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Forming experiment results

The double-curved tool samples were respectively formed under 50 °C, 70 °C, and 90 °C, with a forming rate of 10 kPa/sec. Fig. 4a shows a sample formed at 50 °C, with wrinkles observed in both outer and inner surfaces around the flange. However, no wrinkles were seen in the in-plane zone for this sample. The maximum shear angle was found to be 36° nearby the flange. In all samples, the top surface remained undefomed during the forming process. The parts formed at 70 °C and 90 °C have good surface quality, without wrinkles, as shown in Figs. 4b and c, respectively. However, the diaphragm material stretched more to reach the flange when formed at 90 °C (Fig. 4c) rather than 70 °C (Fig. 4b). Fig. 4d-f show the boundary profiles of each of the three parts formed under selected temperatures using binary image processing. All boundary profiles are close to each other except the one formed at 50 °C (Fig. 4d). The boundary profile of the part formed at 90 °C (Fig 4f) seems symmetrical and close to the desired shape, reflecting the role of resin on the deformability of the prepreg and the resultant stretching of the diaphragm material.

Figure 4: Photographs of samples formed over a double-curved shape and their boundary profiles: (a) and (d) at 50 °C; (b) and (e) at 70 °C; (c) and (f) at 90 °C

In order to investigate the forming rate effect, three samples were formed at 90 °C, with forming rates of 10 kPa/sec, 1.6 kPa/sec and 0.3 kPa/sec, respectively. In terms of surface quality, no wrinkles occurred on any of the samples. However, the outer diameter of the bowl itself was somewhat different for each sample, as shown in Fig. 5. When forming proceeded at a slower rate, the outer diameter of the formed piece was close to the actual shape, while the diameter deviated slightly in case of higher forming rates. Only a single layer was used in this forming experiment; however, the forming-rate parameter investigated here may play an important role in multi-layered forming. All forming experiments indicated that a higher applied pressure within the vacuum box is favorable to accommodate the correct shape, although this conclusion may not hold for other tool geometries. Moreover, the tested material shows a good degree of formability over a complex shape without flaws.

Figure 5: Outer diameters of the parts formed at different forming rates

3.2 Influence of pre-forming state

During the initial step of the forming process, the laminate must be in a flat and tension state to avoid any compression that may lead to wrinkling. In press forming process, blank holders are utilized to apply tensions in the fabric sample prior to forming [22]. Lee *et al.* [23] investigated the effect of blank holders on formed shapes by conducting a stamp-forming experiment on non-crimp fabrics. They found that blank holders reduce the formed shape's asymmetry and influence the NCF's in-plane buckling and wrinkling behavior. Vacuum pressure applied between two diaphragms (clamping force) in diaphragm forming is functionally equivalent to the role of the blank holders. To examine the importance of this factor, one sample was formed at 90 °C without applying a vacuum pressure between the two diaphragms. Fig. 6 shows that severe wrinkles appeared in both the desired shape and the in-plane flat zone. However, high vacuum pressures may reduce fabric deformability during the forming process. Therefore, controlling this factor during the initial forming step is essential in order to avoid compressive states and to reach a higher degree of deformability.

Figure 6: Forming without clamping force between two diaphragms

3.3 Diaphragm Material properties

The diaphragm material used in this study was a translucent silicone rubber (EL1040T). According to the manufacturer, material properties at room temperature are: tensile strength, 12.82 MPa; ultimate elongation, 1300%. A tensile test machine was used to investigate the effect of temperature on the diaphragm material properties. The sample dimensions were 50 mm (wide) by 100 mm (gauge length). Fig. 7 shows the response of the silicon rubber material at temperatures of 50 °C and 90 °C, the temperature range used in the forming of thermosetting composites. Note that material stiffness decreases as temperature increases. Thus, selecting a higher temperature during diaphragm forming can help to accommodate the tool shape by reducing the diaphragm material stiffness. However, overly high temperatures may lead to tearing of the diaphragm material, particularly over sharp-edged shapes.

Figure 7: Uniaxial tensile test of diaphragm material at processing temperatures

3.4 In-plane shear properties

Fig. 8 shows the results of the bias extension test at 50 °C with 20 mm/min. The deformation continues until the shear angle between weft and warp becomes locked. At this “locking angle,” the shear stiffness increases rapidly as the adjacent yarns start to compress each other. Shear resistance decreases significantly with increasing temperature, due to matrix viscosity. Decrease in viscosity can therefore increase the allowable shear deformation. According to Fig. 5, the locking angle of the test material was approximately 48°; however, inter-yarn slippage was observed on the sample before this angle was reached. Wrinkling was evident around the flange in the forming experiment at 50 °C (see Fig. 4a), where the maximum shear angle on the formed part was about 36°. Therefore, the locking angle cannot be only the factor that predicts wrinkling. This finding points to the need for further investigation into the effect of processing parameters and other deformation mechanisms to improve understanding of wrinkling phenomena during the diaphragm forming process.

Figure 8: Bias extension test result at temperature of 50 °C

4. CONCLUSION

A double-diaphragm set-up for forming flat prepreg into complex shapes was developed. Formability of OOA prepreg and the effects of processing parameters were discussed. The results show that selecting a higher temperature within the range of thermosetting resin helps to increase degree of formability and thus produce a formed part without defects. No impact of forming rate on part quality was observed; however, the outer diameter of double-curved parts was found to conform more closely to the original shape when forming proceeded at a slower rate. On a broader level, this study shows that clamping force between two diaphragms has a significant influence on final shape. Reducing the diaphragm material stiffness by selecting higher temperatures is favorable to accommodate the desired shape. Wrinkling during forming is not always correlated with a locked shear angle, as the different results between the bias extension test and the formed part reveal.

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